

Skills 4 eossc

EPOS Data Portal Use Cases

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Deliverable Abstract

This document proposes a collection of Scientific Use Cases that can be used in training settings to showcase the main functionalities of the EPOS Data Portal (Demo, walkthrough done by the trainer) and presented to learners in a hands-on session to give them the opportunity to experiment with the platform and learn by doing how to use it. The Use Cases can be also an inspiration to create your own, tailored on the specific needs of your audience. This document is part of the *D5.3: Learning Path and Training Materials on "Open Science Research Data Management in Solid Earth Sciences"* package.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosC-portal.eu/glossary>

<i>Terminology/Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EPOS	European Plate Observing System
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
RI	Research Infrastructure
RDM	Research Data Management
SES	Solid Earth Science
TCS	Thematic Core Service
ToT	Train-of-Trainers

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1. Executive Summary

a. Introduction – Context

This document proposes a collection of Scientific Use Cases that can be used in training settings to showcase the main functionalities of the EPOS Data Portal (Demo, walkthrough done by the trainer) and presented to learners in a hands-on session to give them the opportunity to experiment with the platform and learn by doing how to use it. The Use Cases can be also an inspiration to create your own, tailored on the specific needs of your audience.

i. Background Information About the Training:

- Description of the objectives
- Before training:
 - Decide the form of training: onsite, online or hybrid
 - Registration form
 - automatic meeting link to all registered participants with event information
 - Email announcement (schedule: ca 1 month before the event or earlier)
- Training outline - agenda + timing
 - Introduction of the EPOS ecosystem (20')
 - Demonstration of EPOS Data Portal by following a scientific user story (20')
 - Hands-on training by following scientific use case & feedback collection through an online form (40')
 - Hands-on walk-through (20')
 - Discussion (20')
- After training:
 - Reporting from the training - analysis of responses and preparing report document
 - Share presentation and/or recording of the training with participants
- *Never done yet: Later feedback collection (about 6 months after training) about the actual portal usage*

ii. General Information:

The use cases are used during the demonstration and hands-on sessions. For the hands-on session in particular, we suggest you prepare the hands-on session by introducing one use case at a time, explaining the user scenario and the tasks to be

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completed. These are described in a form, and can include tips in case the learner gets stuck. Learners access the portal and complete the tasks by retrieving and using data according to the use case specifications. Participants can feed the results obtained in the exercises into the form, together with any feedback about the task, the platform and possible difficulties or issues they encountered in performing it.

One or more trainers should be available during the sessions to answer questions and walk users through the use cases. Trainers should select the most appropriate use cases to be utilized during the training depending on the background of the attendees, or they can create new tailored use cases using the proposed ones as a model.

Important! After you are done with a task, please navigate to the star in the lower left corner and press “clear all favourites”, remove input in “free text search” and remove the “spatial” selection under filters.

2. Scientific Use Cases

a. Scientific Use Case 1 - Volcanism and Earthquakes from Vesuvius in Italy

In this case we will explore the volcanic activity in Naples, Italy. The objective will be to get familiar with **satellite images**, **global navigation satellite system (GNSS)** and **earthquake data** related to **volcanism**, and what scientific information one can derive from the services in the EPOS Data Portal.

Task 1 – Earthquakes around Vesuvius volcano:

- 1.1. Activate the map search tool by clicking the magnifying glass in the upper right corner of the map and type "**Vesuvius**", then hit enter.
- 1.2. Go to **Filters** and activate the spatial selection by clicking the **bounding box** icon. Draw a rectangle (ca 50 x 50 km) around the Vesuvius volcano.
- 1.3. Go to **Free text search** and type "**modern earthquakes**". Select "**Parameters of modern earthquakes (1998-present) - FDSN event**" under **Seismology** and add it to your **favourites** (press the star next to the service title). Probably no data will be shown now since the default minimum magnitude threshold is set to **5**. Modify the "**Minimum magnitude**" to **3** (under "**Advanced search filters**"; expand the menu under the service title and press **Apply**).
- 1.4. **Export** the list of earthquakes **a)** from table view, at the right side of the portal (in **CSV** format); **b)** From the services download menu, within advanced search filters (in **TEXT** format).
- 1.5. Question: When was the **latest earthquake** with a magnitude **above 4.0** that you can identify in the table view?

Task 2 – Satellite Observations:

- 2.1. Navigate to the **satellite icon** in the mid-left side of the portal and select **Satellite Data**. There are 8 services providing data.
- 2.2. Press the **star** icon next to "**LOS Displacement Time Series**" to add the service to your **favourites**.

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2.3. Navigate to the upper right corner of the map, the paper stack symbol, named **Layer and legend control** to find the legend for the service. Move the "**LOS**" layer below the layer with earthquakes.

2.4. Show only the latest image/tile from this service for **orbit 124**.

2.5. Question: What sense of **movement** of the **Vesuvius volcano** summit is visible from **LOS Displacement Time Series** service?

Task 3 – GNSS Observations:

3.1. On the left side of the portal, identify the **GNSS Data and Products** category. Use "free text search" and look for "stations". Find service **GNSS Stations with Products** and add it to your **favourites**.

3.2. Clear the free text search. Look for the service **EPOS GNSS Daily Position Time Series** from **INGV** and add it to your **favourites**. Open the advanced search filters of the service. Replace the "Four character station identification" with "**FRUL**". Then press **Apply**.

3.3. On the right side of the portal, open **GRAPH**. Below the trace selector, press the **plus symbol** next to the **up component**.

3.4. Question: Based on the **up component** in the **graph**, what movement do you observe at **FRUL** station at the beginning of December 2022?

Services:

Seismology : **Parameters of modern earthquakes (1998-present) FDSN event**

Satellite Data : **LOS Displacement Time Series**

GNSS Data and Products : **GNSS Stations with Products**

GNSS Data and Products : **EPOS GNSS Daily Position Time Series by INGV**

b. Scientific Use Case 2 - Volcanism and Earthquakes from Etna in Italy

You as a geoscientist want to explore Etna volcano dynamics in Sicily, Italy. You want to get familiar with **earthquake data, satellite observations and global navigation**

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satellite system (GNSS) data in that area and what scientific information you can retrieve from the EPOS Data Portal.

Task 1 – Geological map:

1.1. Search for “geological map” using the free text search and select **Geological feature View Service (EDGI Geological Map 1.1000,000)**. Add it to your **favourites** by clicking the star icon.

1.2. Below the “free-text search” choose filters, tap the left pulldown menu, and choose “**geolocation**”. Then select **Italy**.

1.3. Activate the map search tool by clicking the magnifying glass in the upper right corner and type “**Sicily**”.

1.4. *Question:* Based on the geological map, what **type** of **rock** is **Mount Etna** mostly **made of**?

- A) Basalt
- B) Dacite
- C) Andesite
- D) I didn’t manage to find

Task 2 – Satellite Observations:

2.1. Navigate to the satellite icon in the mid left side of the portal and select **Satellite Data**.

2.2. Press the **star** icon next to **LOS Displacement Time Series** to add to **favourites**.

2.3. On the map, navigate to eastern **Sicily**, south of mainland **Italy**.

2.4. Navigate to the upper right corner with the paper stack symbol, named **layer and legend control** and find the **legend**.

2.5. *Question:* Can you identify what does the **red colour** mean in the map for the **Line Of Sight (LOS) Displacement Time Series** service?

- A) Stable area
- B) Subsiding area
- C) Uplifting area

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D) I didn't manage to find it.

Task 3 – Volcano Observations

3.1. On the left side of the portal, press the volcano symbol, **Volcano Observations**, and navigate through the services until you find **Mt Etna Earthquake Parameters (2000-2019)** service.

3.2. Open the advanced search filters for the service. Clear all default parameter values, and set the temporal filter from **2000** to **2020**. Override the coordinates and set them to: North: **39**, South: **36**, West: **14**, East: **16**. Set the "**Minimum Md magnitude**" to **3** and "**Minimum MI magnitude**" to **3**, and press the **apply** button.

3.3. Export the list of earthquakes **a)** from table view (in CSV format); **b)** from service download menu in JSON format.

3.4 *Question:* What is the largest earthquake magnitude you can identify in table view?

- A) 3.5
- B) 4.3
- C) 4.8
- D) I didn't manage to find it.

Services:

Geological Information and Modeling : **Geological feature View Service (EDGI Geological Map 1.1000,000)**

Satellite Data : **LOS Displacement Time Series**

Volcano Observations : **Mt Etna Earthquake Parameters (2000-2019)**

c. Scientific Use Case 3 – Fault Systems in Serbia

You as a geoscientist want to explore geoscience in Serbia. You want to get familiar with publicly available earthquake data, fault data and geodetic observations and what scientific information you can retrieve from the EPOS Data Portal.

Task 1 – Earthquakes

1.1. Navigate to "filters" below the free text search and select the dropdown menu on the left side. Select another pulldown menu on the left initially set to "coordinates", set it to **geolocation** and under "select country" scroll down to **Serbia**.

1.2. In the **Free text search** type in "**modern earthquakes**". Select the results below by expanding the "**Seismology**" domain and press the star beside "**Parameters of modern earthquakes (1998-present) - FDSN event**". Modify the "**Minimum magnitude**" to **4** (under "**Advanced search filters**"; expand the menu under the service title and press **Apply**).

1.3. Export the list of earthquakes **a)** from table view, at the right side of the portal (in CSV format); **b)** From the services download menu, within advanced search filters (in TEXT format).

1.4 *Question:* When was the latest earthquake with a magnitude above 4.0 that you can identify in the table view?

Task 2 – Fault models:

2.1. Navigate to the **Seismology icon** in the mid-left side of the portal and browse until you find **European Fault Source Model 2020 (OGC WMS)**. Press the **star** next to the service to add to **favorites**.

2.2. *Question:* There seems to be a **relation between the fault zones in Serbia and the stronger earthquakes**. Can you find what type of fault system the light green faults represent?

- A) Normal fault (N)
- B) Reverse fault (R)

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- C) Left-lateral (LL) – Strike-slip fault
- D) Right-lateral (RL) – Strike-slip fault
- E) I didn't manage to find
- F) Other

Task 3 – GNSS Observations:

3.1. On the left side of the portal, identify the GNSS Data and Products category. Use "free text search" and look for "stations". Find the service **GNSS Stations with Products** and add it to your favorites. In map view navigate to the GNSS station in South West Serbia close to Novi Pazar. Copy the **first 4 letters** from the **GNSS Station ID**.

3.2. Clear the free text search. Look for the service **EPOS GNSS Daily Position Time Series from INGV** and add it to your **favorites**. Open the advanced search filters of this service. **Replace** the **"Four character station identification"** with the four letters you copied from the GNSS station in the previous step. Then press **Apply**.

3.3. On the right side of the portal, open **"GRAPH"**. Below the **"trace selector"**, press the **"plus symbol"** next to the **"Up component"**.

3.4. *Question:* Based on the **up component** in the graph, what movement do you observe at **NPAZ station** between Jul 2020 and Jan 2021?

Services:

Seismology : **Parameters of Modern Earthquakes (1998-present) FDSN event**

Seismology : **European Fault Source Model 2020 (OGC WMS)**

GNSS Data and Products : **GNSS Stations with Products**

GNSS Data and Products : **EPOS GNSS Daily Position Time Series by INGV**

d. Scientific Use Case 4 – Satellite Imagery, Volcanism and Earthquakes on Iceland:

In this case we will explore the **volcanic activity** in Iceland. The objective will be to get familiar with **satellite images** and **earthquake data** related to volcanism, and what scientific information one can derive from the services in the EPOS Data Portal.

1. Access the EPOS Data Portal and navigate to “**filters**” in the upper left corner, press the pulldown arrow and input these coordinates: N:**65**, S:**63**. W:**-25**, E:**-21**. And input “**2021**” and “**2022**” in the temporal fields. Press the confirm symbol.
2. In the EPOS Data Portal, select the **Satellite Observation** icon in the left menu in the portal and choose the service listed under Services, in the next paragraph of this document. Then press the star icon to **add to favourites**.
3. In map view, identify an area with high colour contrast, a region with both blue and red beside each other. Have a look at the legend to see what these colours represent. What geological process do you think is present in this area?
4. Search for “**Parameters of modern earthquakes (1998-present) – FDSN event**” in the free text search field and browse to the seismology icon on the left side and **add to favourites**.
5. For “**Parameters of modern earthquakes (1998-present) – FDSN event**”, select the advanced search filters and specify minimum magnitude of the earthquakes to “4”, and press “Apply”. In table view browse through the timing of the earthquake events listed. Is there a trend in the temporal distribution of these earthquakes?
6. Note the distribution of the earthquakes in map view in relation to the satellite imagery. What geological process do you think is the cause of the earthquakes?

Services:

Satellite Observations : **Unwrapped Interferograms**

Seismology : **Parameters of modern earthquakes (1998-present) – FDSN event**

e. Scientific Use Case 5 – Arctic Tsunami Hazard Model in Norway:

In this case we will explore **submarine landslide deposits** and calculated probabilities of **tsunamis** in a particular area in the **arctic**, outside the North-West coast of Norway.

1. In the EPOS Data Portal, select the two services under the services paragraph here, by going to the seismology and tsunami icon on the left side.

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2. Navigate to “filters” in the upper left corner and input these coordinates N:**66**, S:**61**. W:**0**, E:**7** and press the **confirm symbol**.
3. In the free text search field search for “**Parameters of modern earthquakes (1998-present) – FDSN event**”. Press the down arrow on the side of the service to access “**advanced search filters**” and specify minimum magnitude to **2**, then press “**apply**”.
4. Question: Explore the distribution of earthquakes, do you think the seismicity along the Norwegian coast is sufficient to trigger submarine landslides?

Services:

Tsunami : **EMSS21 Euro-Mediterranean Submarine landslide database – Arctic deposits (OGC WMS)**

Seismology : **Parameters of modern earthquakes (1998-present) – FDSN event**

f. Scientific Use Case 6 – Ancient Arctic Tsunamis In Norway:

In this case we will explore **ancient submarine landslide deposits** of **tsunamis** in a particular area in the **arctic**, outside the North-West coast of Norway.

1. In the EPOS Data Portal, select the two tsunami services listed in the next paragraph by going to the tsunami icon on the left side.
2. Navigate to “filters” in the upper left corner and input these coordinates N:**66**, S:**61**. W:**0**, E:**7** and press the confirm symbol.
3. On the map, press one of the circle point markers along the Norwegian coast. From the pop-up, open the external link located beside **hc_link**. Read briefly about “The NEAM Tsunami Hazard Model 2018”. Read about the red line of 50th percentile and determine: A) The maximum inundation height, and B) probability of exceeding that height in 50 years?

Services:

Tsunami : **Euro-Mediterranean Submarine landslide database (EMSS21) – Arctic deposits (OGC WMS)**

Tsunami : **NEAM Tsunami Hazard Model 2018 full dataset (OGC WFS)**

g. Scientific Use Case 7 – Ancient Tsunami Reconstruction in Italy

In this case we will **investigate old tsunamis in Italy** and see if we can **correlate** the tsunami with a **historical earthquake**.

1. In the EPOS Data Portal, select the seismology and the tsunami service under the paragraph services.
2. Navigate to “filters” in the upper left corner and input these coordinates N:**43**, S:**41**, W:**13**, E:**15** and press the **confirm symbol**.
3. Press the down arrow on the side of the historical earthquake service to access “advanced search filters” and specify “**minimum magnitude**” to **6** and “**limit the no. of entries**” to **10** and press the “apply” button.
4. In the map view press the pop-up from “**Italian Tsunami Effects Database – Tsunami History WFS**” named “**Gaeta**”, in Rome at the map. Open the external link and read when the Tsunami occurred and what the expected cause is. Note the date.
5. From “**Parameters of historical earthquakes (1000-1899) – FDSN**” present in map view, could you find an earthquake that matches the timing of the Rome Tsunami? If so, what was the magnitude? Use table or map view to explore the different event timings.

Services:

Seismology : **Parameters of historical earthquakes (1000-1899) – FDSN**

Tsunami : **Italian Tsunami Effects Database - Tsunami History WFS (ITED V1)**

h. Scientific Use Case 8 – Natural or Anthropogenic Hazards in Poland:

This case aims to **identify** the **source** of the **sinking areas** in Poland; **these** regions also have recorded **seismicity**. Is there a way to **determine** if the source of these **hazards** is **natural** or **anthropogenic**?

Services:

Seismology : **Parameters of modern earthquakes (1998-present) – FDSN event**

Anthropogenic Hazards : **Multiple services**

Hints:

Hover over the thematic core services in the left menu, can you find the word hazard and see if some of the service thereunder match up with the seismic activity?

i. Scientific Use Case 9 – Explore Services Around Your Area, Europe:

This is an **open case** where you **explore** the area around your **hometown**, to see what kind of services of interest are available.

1. Access the data portal and make note of the number of services. Then go to “filters” and select the “rectangular selection tool” and make a square around your home location on the map. Note that the number of services in the left menu are reduced.
2. In the left menu, select the thematic core services of interest to you.

Tips and suggestions:

Tip 1: Browse seismology – Page 3 – Parameters of modern earthquakes (1998-present) – FDSN event. Press the down arrow, specify minimum magnitude to **2** and press “**apply**”. Is there a trend in seismicity, what do you think the reason behind this is? To further explore, browse seismology – Page 1 – Seismogenic Faults (OGC WMS), is the seismicity located near by a fault or are there other sources of seismicity?

Tip 2: Access “Anthropogenic hazards” if there are any services in your area. Press “i” for details and read the description. What kind of hazard is this, and what is the main cause?

Tip 3: Access “Satellite Data” and select “LOS Displacement Time Series”. Make note of the distribution of colours, access the “**layer and legend tool**” in the upper right corner and look at the legend for “LOS Displacement Time Series (images)”. In the map, are there any colours that are either red (represents > 2 cm/year sinking) or purples (represents > 2 cm/year rising). What do you think is the cause of these displacements? Are these related to recorded anthropogenic hazards or natural phenomena like earthquakes or volcanoes?

Tip 4: Now, see if you can combine some of the services previously introduced to give an overview over the geological issues in your area.

External links

- EPOS Data Portal on YouTube:
 - <https://www.youtube.com/@EposProjectEu/playlists>
- EPOS Data Portal Training Complete Event 25.01.2024:
 - <https://youtu.be/YeqW1Qp1L6g>
- EPOS Data Portal Training Event Intro and demo 25.01.24:
 - https://youtu.be/kszG_w0ASDc
- EPOS Data Portal Training May 2023:
 - <https://youtu.be/GzThnjmzXe8>

Feedback forms attached in this folder as .xls